

An Artificial Enzyme: How Nanoconfinement Allows the Selective Electrochemical Detection of Glucose Directly in Whole Blood

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Nanoparticles that catalyze biochemically relevant reactions are promoted as alternative enzymes. The application of such artificial enzymes is severely restricted by poor selectivity in biological fluids; mainly because the reactions occur at active sites on the exterior surface of the nanoparticle. Enzymes in contrast typically have their active sites down a nanoconfined substrate channel where the reaction occurs in different solution conditions to bulk solution which aids in achieving selectivity for the substrate. Herein the same 3D structure of enzymes is mimicked in nanoparticles to allow selective reactions in biological fluids. This is achieved using a gold nanoparticle coated in a conducting mesoporous carbon shell where isolated nanochannels lead to the gold surface. It can detect glucose in whole blood with no interference from other species. This is achieved by electrochemically pulsing the artificial enzymes to generate the locally required alkalinity for an effective electrocatalytic reaction in the nanochannels, as well as expelling fouling agents that will otherwise passivate the electrocatalytic reaction. The artificial enzymes are shown to be capable of detecting glucose in biological fluids, without loss of signal, for several months. This study shows how nanoconfinement in nanoparticles can be exploited to potentially allow a broad range of species to be selectively detected in biological fluids with stability that can exceed that of enzymes.

monitoring, remediation devices, labels in immunoassays for the diagnosis of diseases, and in cleaning products. The application of enzymes in biomedical devices, however, can be limited by the stability of a given enzyme.^[1] This has attracted interest in developing enzyme mimics, that is artificial enzymes that are significantly more stable than their biological inspiration.^[2] Mimicking the molecular structure of the enzyme active site alone has resulted in catalysts with exceptional efficiency.^[3] The major existing hurdle that still exists is fabricating stable materials that can mimic the substrate selectivity as well as the exceptional activity of enzymes at catalyzing reactions in complex biological fluids.^[4]

Here we address this challenge by mimicking not the active site of an enzyme but rather their 3D structure where the active site is located down a nanoconfined channel.^[5] Part of the importance of the active site being down a nanochannel in many enzymes is that the solution environment where the reaction proceeds is different from bulk.^[6] The alteration of the solution environment not only facilitates achieving

high activity but also high selectivity via being able to exclude undesirable species from accessing the nanoconfined space.

The strategy of mimicking the 3D structure of enzymes has only been made possible through advances in nanomaterial

1. Introduction

Enzymes are extremely efficient catalysts and have been explored in a plethora of applications, such as glucose meters for diabetes

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DOI: 10.1002/adfm.202400322

synthesis that have allowed the investigation of nanoconfinement in electrocatalysis,^[7] sensing,^[8] and chemical synthesis.^[9] The initial forays into nanoconfinement for electrocatalysis have shown that nanoparticles that mimic the geometric features of enzymes can be used to control the local solution environment,^[10] increasing the local concentration of reactants to give a significantly higher specific activity than achievable without nanoconfinement,^[11] and to facilitate multistep cascade reaction occurring at different catalytic sites.^[12] However, thus far, control of local environment using nanoconfinement has not been exploited to provide selectivity for a specific reactant within a biological milieu.

We chose glucose oxidation as a model reaction due to its large industrial importance, and the need for long-term enzyme stability when used for continuous blood glucose biosensors.^[13] Current efforts to develop non-enzymatic glucose sensors based on direct electrooxidation of glucose have been limited by the low selectivity of such catalysts, and by the fact they rely on alkaline electrolytes for suitable sensitivity. The most successful strategy is to use either gold or platinum as a catalytic surface for glucose oxidation, but this strategy requires both a highly basic pH and the exclusion of chloride to minimize poisoning of the catalyst surface.^[14] Therefore to develop an artificial enzyme based on a solid nanoparticle we need to achieve three things. These are to 1) exclude chloride, 2) generate a high pH, and 3) exclude fouling by proteins and cells for the catalysts to be used directly in unadulterated biological fluids.

Our artificial enzyme that mimics the architecture of enzymes consists of a nanoparticle with a gold core and a shell made of, chemically modified, isolated carbon nanochannels (Figure 1A). The chemically modified carbon nanochannels prevent fouling species from blocking the access of the reactant to the gold active sites located down the nanochannels whilst ensuring the walls do not react with glucose. An electrochemical potential pulsing protocol has been designed to exclude interferents and poisoning species as well as to alter the solution environment inside the nanochannels to alkaline conditions to facilitate the oxidation of glucose at the gold surface (Figure 1B). In this way, the reaction conditions can be controlled to allow the selective detection of glucose directly in whole blood, so important for glucose sensors in diabetes monitoring.

2. Results and Discussion

The use of gold and other metallic nanoparticles for non-enzymatic glucose detection has been extensively reported but these nanoparticles cannot be used directly in whole blood. This is because not only do these nanoparticles require alkaline pH to be catalytically active for glucose oxidation, but they are also poisoned by chloride ions and fouled by proteins, both present in high concentrations in whole blood.^[14] To overcome these challenges, we designed gold nanoparticles coated with carbon shell consisting of isolated mesopores (nanochannels) that extended all the way through to the underlying gold surface to allow the exclusion of undesirable species and to electrochemically generate the alkaline pH directly within the nanochannels for subsequent glucose oxidation (Figure 1A; Figure S1, Supporting Information). The channels are estimated for the electron micrographs to be ≈ 8 nm in diameter and (4.7 ± 1.2) nm in length.

This was achieved by applying a series of 90 two-step potential pulses (Figure 1B) taking a total time of 27 s. The first potential step to -1.85 V for 0.2 s (reduction – purple shaded in top left of Figure 1C, all potentials are versus Ag|AgCl|NaCl 3 mol L⁻¹) generates hydroxide ions via electrochemical reduction of oxygen and water. The local alkaline environment then facilitates the electrochemical glucose oxidation during the subsequent potential step at -0.25 V for 0.1 s (oxidation – green shaded in top right of Figure 1C). Note, the overpotential for the water reduction reaction is ≈ 300 mV more positive on Au than on carbon, which means that the hydroxide ions are predominantly generated at the Au surface at the bottom of the nanochannels (Figure S2, Supporting Information). This can be seen in Figure S2 (Supporting Information) where it is evident that on gold as the potential was scanned negatively first oxygen in the nanochannels was reduced at potentials ≈ -0.60 V versus Ag|AgCl|NaCl 3 mol L⁻¹ and then water at potentials more negative than -1.15 V. The currents at the end of each oxidation step of each of the 90 pulses, performed in phosphate buffer electrolyte (0.0302 mol L⁻¹ Na²HPO₄ + 0.0098 mol L⁻¹ NaH₂PO₄ + 0.1 mol L⁻¹ KCl; pH 7.4), were collected (Figure 1D; see Figure S3, Supporting Information for full chronoamperograms) and summed up to produce the glucose calibration plots (Figure 1E). We note that initially, the current in Figure 1D increases, which we attribute to the removal of chloride ions from the channels and the generation of the highly alkaline environment, after which the current stabilizes.

Electrochemical glucose oxidation on gold at physiological pH was possible due to a combination of the nanoconfined environment where the gold active sites are located and the electrochemical pulsing protocol to generate OH⁻ locally. No glucose detection was observed when the reduction potential pulse was not sufficiently negative to produce OH⁻ on either gold nanorods (no confinement – green circles of left-hand side plot in Figure 2A) or with the artificial enzymes (green circles of right-hand side plot in Figure 2A). With electrochemical pulsing, a glucose oxidation current was observed with the uncoated nanorods (blue circles of left-hand side plot in Figure 2A) but it was approximately five times lower than the magnitude observed with the artificial enzymes (blue circles of right-hand side plot in Figure 2A), even though the area of exposed gold of the artificial enzymes was approximately eight times smaller with the artificial enzymes relative to the uncoated nanoparticles (Figure S4, Supporting Information). The increased catalytic activity of the artificial enzymes shows that the nanoconfined environment provides a much higher local concentration of hydroxide ions than in the absence of nanoconfinement.

In addition to providing the local alkaline environment, the reduction potential pulse in nanoconfinement also prevented electrode surface poisoning by chloride ions, present in high concentrations in blood and other biological fluids. Whilst the glucose oxidation current with the uncoated nanorods was significantly lower in the electrolyte with chloride than in the electrolyte without chloride (blue and orange plots respectively of left-hand side plot in Figure 2B), with the artificial enzyme the oxidation currents were in fact marginally higher in the presence of chloride than in absence of chloride (blue and orange plots respectively of right-hand side plot in Figure 2B). The higher catalytic activity with the artificial enzymes in the chloride-containing electrolyte is possibly due to increased ionic conductivity of the bulk

Figure 1. A) Enzymatic electrochemical sensors have high activity and selectivity, which are related to enzymes having active sites located down a substrate channel, allowing control of the local environment. The *artificial enzyme* contains the gold active sites located down electrically conducting but catalytic inert nanochannels (cartoons on the right-hand side). The transmission electron microscopy (TEM) image (top) shows the gold nanorod coated with a thin carbon shell and the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image (bottom) shows the top view of the vertically aligned carbon nanochannels. B) The electrochemical control of the local environment was achieved by applying 90 consecutive 2-step potential pulses taking a total time of 27 s to collect the data. C) The reduction potential pulse (-1.85 V for 0.2 s, purple – left) produces OH^- locally inside the nanochannels to render the gold highly catalytically active for glucose and removes undesirable species such as chloride ions and electroactive interferences. The combination of the nanochannel structure with the reduction potential pulse also prevents non-specific adsorption of fouling proteins. Glucose oxidation happens during the subsequent oxidation potential pulse (-0.25 V for 0.1 s, green – right). D) The current at the end of each oxidation pulse was collected for measurements done at different glucose concentrations and summed up to produce the plot in E. Electrolyte = $0.0302 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 + 0.0098 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 + 0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ KCl}$. All potentials are reported against the $\text{Ag}|\text{AgCl}||\text{NaCl } 3 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ reference electrode.

electrolyte when the ionic strength is higher (0.1004 and $0.2004 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ for chloride-free and chloride-containing electrolytes, respectively). Although higher ionic conductivity can influence mass transport with the uncoated nanorods, any advantage was offset by significant chloride adsorption on the gold sur-

face in absence of nanoconfinement. Note that exclusion of anionic chloride from the channels whilst maintaining a high pH in the channels with anionic hydroxide ions may appear contradictory. Certainly, the hydroxide is expected also to be repelled from the channels by the highly negative potentials but is also being

Figure 2. A) The effect of nanoconfinement and a reduction potential pulse to reduce oxygen and water under formation of hydroxide and increase the pH on the glucose oxidation activity and B) The effect of nanoconfinement in preventing chloride poisoning. Au nanorods (left) and nanoconfined nanoparticles (right). Blue circles: -1.85 V reduction pulsing in the chloride-containing electrolyte; orange circles: -1.85 V reduction pulsing in the chloride-free electrolyte; green circles: -0.5 V reduction pulsing in chloride-containing electrolyte. Each point in all plots is the sum of the current at the end of each oxidation potential pulse from the 90 two-step potential pulses; oxidation pulse: -0.25 V for 0.1 s . Electrolyte: phosphate buffer ($\text{pH } 7.4$, $0.0302 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 + 0.0098 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 + 0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ KCl}$, except for data in orange where a chloride free electrolyte was used). All potentials are reported against the $\text{Ag}|\text{AgCl}|\text{NaCl } 3 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ reference electrode.

generated at a very high rate at the gold surface, thus allowing a pH to remain very high. The high pH is confirmed by the fact that the oxidation potential for glucose, which changes as a function of pH, is much more negative than it would normally be expected for physiological pH.^[17]

The high activity in the nanoconfined volumes resulting from the local alkaline environment and absence of chloride poisoning, allowed glucose to be oxidized at a potential as low as -0.25 V , a much less positive potential than is usually possible even in the highly alkaline solutions adopted as electrolytes in non-enzymatic systems (Figure S5, Supporting Information).^[17] The very low oxidation potential also means that the system is selective against other common electroactive species in blood, such as uric acid and ascorbic acid as seen in Figure 3A where no interfering currents were observed when physiological con-

centrations of the electroactive interfering species were added in the electrolyte (more details in, Figure S6, Supporting Information). Note other sugars that are present in the bloodstream also give minimal interfering currents (Figure S7, Supporting Information).

The influence of the electrochemical pulsing in nanoconfinement on preventing protein fouling was also assessed. Human serum albumin (HSA), a protein present in blood at concentrations close to saturation ($30\text{--}35 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$), accounts for $\approx 60\%$ of the total protein present in blood and is the main species causing electrode fouling.^[18] Although a decrease in the oxidation currents was observed in the electrolyte containing 35 mg mL^{-1} HSA compared to the electrolyte in absence of HSA, glucose was detected in the presence of the fouling protein with the artificial enzymes (Figure 3B, filled circles), whilst no glucose detection was

Figure 3. A) Effect of adding electroactive interferents on the oxidation current. The measurements with 6 mmol L^{-1} glucose were repeated 3 times and the measurements with each interferent (urate and ascorbate) were repeated 2 times each. B) Effect of adding human serum albumin (HSA – 35 mg mL^{-1}) as the fouling species to the chloride-free phosphate buffer electrolyte with the artificial enzymes (full circles) and uncoated gold nanorods (open circles). C) Capacitive current subtracted glucose oxidation voltammetric peak without (black) and with (dark red) 35 mg mL^{-1} HSA added to the electrolyte; uncoated Au nanorods (top) and artificial enzymes (bottom). D) Glucose oxidation voltammetric peak of the first 7 cycles with artificial enzymes containing 35 mg mL^{-1} HSA before (top) and after (bottom) capacitive current subtraction. For A and B: the data is the sum of the current of 90 pulses as a function of glucose concentration; reduction potential pulse = -1.85 V for 0.15 s A) and 0.20 s B); oxidation potential pulse = -0.25 V for 0.1 s . For C and D: the voltammograms were recorded between -0.1 and 1.2 V at 50 mV s^{-1} . Electrolyte: phosphate buffer (pH 7.4, $0.0302 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 + 0.0098 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ NaH}_2\text{PO}_4$) without and with 6 mmol L^{-1} glucose. All potentials are reported against the $\text{Ag}|\text{AgCl}|\text{NaCl}$ 3 mol L^{-1} reference electrode.

observed with the uncoated nanorods (Figure 3B, open circles). Although there are many catalytic nanoparticles for the nonenzymatic detection of glucose that operate in the physiological range (See Table S1, Supporting Information for a range of examples), as far as we are aware this is the first example of a nonenzymatic glucose sensor being able to detect glucose in the presence of physiological amounts of protein let alone whole blood. The ability of the artificial enzymes to resist fouling is attributed to the reduction pulses repelling the negatively charged protein (the isoelectric point of HSA is 4.8) and the nanoconfined channels acting as a filter that prevents protein adsorption on the Au sites. Note the 8 nm channels are smaller than the HSA molecules ($\approx 15 \text{ nm}$ long). The decrease in oxidation current when HSA is added in the electrolyte is then mostly attributed to partial blocking of the nanochannel entrance by the fouling proteins as they

adsorb on the carbon nanochannel surface rather than HSA adsorption directly on the gold surface.

The adsorption of HSA on the carbon nanochannel surface was evident from cyclic voltammetry measurements performed in electrolytes containing HSA (Figure 3C). A glucose oxidation peak current was observable in presence of HSA with the artificial enzymes (dark red line in Figure 3C – bottom) although the peak was smaller than in absence of HSA (black line in Figure 3C – bottom). No oxidation peak was observed with the uncoated nanorods in the electrolyte containing HSA (Figure 3C – top). The cyclic voltammograms enable us to deconvolute the effect of fouling on the faradaic current arising from glucose oxidation and the capacitive current arising from surface adsorption of charged species on the carbon surface. Background capacitance subtraction of the voltammograms shows that the decrease

Figure 4. Stability of nanoconfined nanoparticles in electrolytes containing human serum albumin (HSA) with no added glucose (gray), with 6 mmol L⁻¹ glucose (orange) and 12 mmol L⁻¹ glucose (blue). The electrode was rinsed with HSA-free electrolyte and kept dried in between the measurements. Each measurement is the sum of the current at the end of each oxidation potential pulse from the 90 two-step potential pulses; reduction pulse: -1.85 V for 0.2 s and oxidation pulse: -0.25 V for 0.1 s. Electrolyte: phosphate buffer (pH 7.4, 0.0302 mol L⁻¹ Na₂HPO₄ + 0.0098 mol L⁻¹ NaH₂PO₄ + 0.1 mol L⁻¹ KCl + 35 mg mL⁻¹ HSA. All potentials are reported against the Ag|AgCl|NaCl 3 mol L⁻¹ reference electrode.

in current with repeated voltammetric sweeps in the electrolyte containing HSA is due to a decrease in the background capacitive current caused by non-specific adsorption of HSA on the carbon surface, (compare Figure 3D – top and bottom) as no significant change in the faradaic current arising from glucose oxidation was observed with cycling after subtraction of the background capacitance.

Next, the stability of the artificial enzymes during electrochemical measurements was assessed (Figure 4). The measurements were performed in electrolytes containing physiological levels of both chloride ions and HSA in absence of glucose and with 6 and 12 mmol L⁻¹ of glucose added into the electrolyte. The electrode was rinsed with buffer and kept dried in between measurements. The electrode was stable for at least 80 days, with a distinct increase in current observed when increasing concentrations of glucose were added into the electrolyte. These results show that the physical barrier provided by the nanochannels combined with the potential pulsing protocol to expel the negatively charged species were able to maintain the active sites available for glucose oxidation in the presence of both poisoning chloride and fouling protein species over a prolonged period of time.

The results in HSA in Figure 4 show that the electrochemical pulsing protocol in nanoconfined volumes allows glucose detection in the presence of fouling proteins and other species that are in whole blood. Measurements were next performed in whole blood without added glucose, where a significant current decrease was observed over time, with 70% current retention after 2 h decreasing to 30% after 7 h (shaded area in Figure 5A – open circles). The decrease in current is attributed to non-specific adsorption of proteins on the surface outside of the nanochannels over time. This protein adsorption decreases the background (capacitive) current as no faradaic reaction occurs in the absence of glucose and in accordance with the voltammetry measurements performed in electrolytes containing HSA (Figure 3D).

To prevent the decrease in background current over time, the surface of the carbon nanochannels of the artificial enzymes

was then chemically modified with a low-impedance zwitterionic phenyl layer (phenyl phosphorylcholine – PPC)^[19] as an anti-fouling agent (see Figure S8, Supporting Information for more details, including a scheme of the surface chemistry). The resulting PPC-modified artificial enzymes retained the background current during the oxidation potential pulses in whole blood for at least 42 h, with just a 5% current decrease observed within the first hour (Figure 5A – full circles). The highly stable background current in whole blood obtained with the PPC-modified artificial enzymes is attributed to a combination of the hydrophilic surface provided by the PPC layer and the electrochemical pulsing protocol. The hydrophilic surface mitigates against the proteins strongly adsorbing onto the carbon surface; the loosely bound proteins are expected to be easily expelled from the electrode surface during the reduction potential pulses. The role of the potential pulses in removing weakly adsorbed proteins from the electrode surface was evident when the electrode containing the PPC-modified artificial enzymes was left immersed in blood without applying any potential (i.e., at open circuit potential – OCP) for a time interval in between the measurements. When the electrode was left immersed in blood at OCP, a decrease in the background current was observed that became greater with time. This decrease in the background current when PPC was employed, was recovered with repeated potential pulsing irrespectively of the time at OCP (Figure 5A – full circles). Note with the unmodified artificial enzymes, the contribution of the potential pulses to remove the fouling proteins was minimal, being only observed in the first pulses but becoming rapidly overcome by the irreversible protein adsorption on the electrode surface (Figure 5A – open circles).

Finally, the capability of the electrochemical potential pulsing protocol and the nanoconfinement in these artificial enzymes to electrochemically detect glucose in whole blood was tested using the PPC-modified artificial enzymes. A linear increase of the oxidation current with increasing concentration of glucose added into whole blood was observed between 4 and 16 mmol L⁻¹ as

Figure 5. A) Effect of carbon nanochannels surface modification with PPC (phenyl phosphorylcholine) on background current stability in whole blood without added glucose (full circles = PPC-modified artificial enzymes and open circles = unmodified artificial enzymes). 10 subsequent repetitions of 90 two-step pulses were performed with the sensor being at open circuit potential (OCP) between measurements. The electrode was kept immersed in blood at all times. B) Glucose detection in whole blood, showing a linear correlation between current and glucose concentration up to 16 mmol L⁻¹; for each glucose concentration, 10 measurements of 90 two-step potentials pulses were made and the data shown is the average of the last 5 measurements. For all measurements, the data is the summation of currents at the end of each oxidation pulse in the series of 90 two-step pulses. Potential pulse conditions: -1.85 V for 0.2 s and -0.25 V for 0.3 s. All potentials are reported against the Ag|AgCl|NaCl 3 mol L⁻¹ reference electrode.

shown in Figure 5B. The data is the average of the oxidation currents of the last 5 out of 10 subsequent series of two-step pulses, showing the stability of the currents after each glucose addition. The last 5 out of a sequence of 10 measurements were used to ensure that the background current was recovered before collecting the data, since the electrode was maintained at OCP while glucose was added into the electrolyte, causing the background current to decrease due to protein adsorption (see Figure S9, Supporting Information for all data points). These results show that the potential pulsing protocol, combined with nanoconfinement, can control the local nanoconfined environment at the gold surface located down the carbon nanochannels, allowing selective glucose detection in a complex biological fluid such as whole blood.

3. Conclusion

Herein it is shown how isolated mesoporous carbon channels around a catalytic gold nanorod allow the detection of glucose at

the gold surface in unadulterated whole blood. This is achieved by exploiting a combination of nanoconfinement in the channel which means the solution conditions where the reaction is occurring are different from the bulk blood and electrochemical potential pulsing to manipulate the solution conditions inside the nanochannels to facilitate the electrocatalytic reaction. The direct oxidation of glucose on gold surfaces is most effective at highly basic pH values and with chloride ions, that poison the electrode surface, excluded. In whole blood, the exclusion of proteins that foul the electrode and other electroactive species that might contribute to a current is also required for selective measurement of glucose. To overcome these challenges, we designed a catalytic gold nanorod particle with a mesoporous carbon coating that is conducting but not active for glucose oxidation. Applying a potential to an underlying carbon electrode will then influence the electrochemical reactions occurring inside the nanochannels and hence influence the solution conditions inside these channels above the catalytic gold surface. To achieve the detection of glucose in unadulterated whole blood, the potential is first pulsed

at -1.85 V to generate hydroxide via the reduction of water, to achieve alkaline pH values, and simultaneously expel chloride and other negatively charged species from the channel. The potential was then pulsed back to -0.25 V to allow the oxidation of glucose. The high pH in the nanoconfined channels facilitates a highly catalytically active surface for glucose whilst the very low oxidation potential for glucose of -0.25 V, a much less positive potential than is usually possible even in the highly alkaline solutions, means that the system is selective against other electroactive species in blood. The nanoparticles themselves are highly stable over long time periods and we show this allows them to continue to record reliable glucose measurements in blood over many hours and continue to show no signal change over 80 days (Figure 4). This makes these artificial enzymes ideal for both continuous glucose monitoring and for classical glucose finger prick devices.

The implications of this work, however, are much greater than being able to selectively detect glucose in whole blood, as important as that is. The broader implications of this work are that we show using catalytic nanoparticles how to selectively detect small molecule species of interest in complex biological media in a way typically only achievable with enzymes. We show how mimicking the geometry of enzymes, where the reaction happens down a nanoconfined channel such that the solution composition adjacent to the active site is very different to the bulk medium in which the analyte is found, allows selective detection of species. We also show that having a nanochannel material that is electrochemically inactive for the analyte but electrochemically conducting, provides the basis for the use of electrochemical pulsing to control both the solution conditions inside the nanochannels and the potential at which the detection reaction occurs. This is a capability not achievable with an insulating polypeptide shell in natural enzymes. We show that our artificial enzymes, with enzyme-like geometry, cannot only achieve selective detection in the way that enzymes do but they also have advantages concerning the stability of the recognition elements in a sensor and advantages in how to tune the detection reaction. We believe these principles will be transferrable to other analytes and other artificial enzyme systems.

4. Experimental Section

Synthesis of the Au Core-Carbon Nanochannels Shell Nanoparticles (Artificial Enzymes): Au Nanorods: Au nanorods were synthesized using a seed growth procedure.^[15] First, Au seeds were obtained by adding HAuCl_4 (50 mmol L^{-1} , $50 \mu\text{L}$) to an aqueous solution of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB - 0.1 mol L^{-1} , 10 mL). NaBH_4 (50 mmol L^{-1} , 0.6 mL , freshly prepared and kept in an ice bath) was then added under vigorous stirring for 2 min. The seed solution was left undisturbed for 30 min before using it. For the nanorods, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB - 7 g) and sodium oleate ($\text{NaOL} - 1.234 \text{ g}$) were dissolved in 250 mL of water by stirring at 50°C . The mixture was then cooled to room temperature and AgNO_3 (10 mmol L^{-1} , 7.2 mL) was added. After leaving the mixture for 15 min, 245 mL of water and HAuCl_4 (50 mmol L^{-1} , 5 mL) were added and the yellow mixture was stirred for 90 min, becoming transparent within the first 20–30 min of stirring. HCl (32% , 1.5 mL) was added after 90 min and the mixture was stirred for another 15 min. Ascorbic acid (64 mmol L^{-1} , 1.25 mL) was added followed by vigorous stirring for 30 s. Au seeds (0.4 mL) were added and the mixture was stirred for another 1 min before being left undisturbed overnight in the dark when the mixture became dark red.

Synthesis of the Au Core-Carbon Nanochannels Shell Nanoparticles (Artificial Enzymes): Carbon Coating: The procedure was adapted from a nano-emulsion assembly approach to produce mesoporous carbon nanospheres.^[16] Pluronic F127 (96 mg) and dopamine hydrochloride (48 mg) were dissolved in a mixture of water and ethanol (4.8 mL of each) in a 20 mL glass vial. Then, mesitylene ($195 \mu\text{L}$) was added dropwise using a syringe with the needle immersed inside the solution and under stirring at 375 rpm for 30 min. Au nanorods (60 mL in $4 \times 15 \text{ mL}$ centrifuge tubes – centrifuged and washed 1x with water at 6500 rpm for 25 min) were added by taking $\approx 1 \text{ mL}$ of the emulsion to disperse the nanorods and transfer them from the centrifuge tube to the reaction vial. NH_4OH ($495 \mu\text{L}$) was then quickly added to the reaction and the emulsion was stirred for 15 min after which the reaction mixture was immediately centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 25 min, followed by washing with water + ethanol ($1:1 \text{ v.v.}$, $3 \times$, 8000 rpm , 8 min) and dispersed in ethanol.

Thermal treatment was performed to first remove the surfactant and then to transform the polydopamine coating into carbon. The polydopamine-coated Au nanorods, dispersed in ethanol, were transferred to a silica combustion boat and the ethanol was evaporated at 120°C . The boat was transferred to a tube furnace and heated under argon flow from room temperature to 350°C in 5 h to remove the surfactant, then heated up to 700°C in an hour and maintained at 700°C for another 45 min to convert the polydopamine to carbon by pyrolysis. After cooling down to room temperature under argon, the obtained nanoparticles were retrieved from the boat by scratching them into a small amount of added isopropanol using a plastic tip. The morphology of the obtained artificial enzymes was analyzed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) using a FEI Tecnai G2 20 TEM microscope and by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using a JEOL JSM-IT800SHL Ultra High-Resolution FE SEM microscope.

Electrochemical Measurements: Electrode Preparation: The artificial enzymes dispersed in isopropanol were centrifuged and re-dispersed in water ($150 \mu\text{L}$) to form an ink of which $7.5 \mu\text{L}$ ($3 \times 2.5 \mu\text{L}$) were drop-casted onto a 0.07 cm^2 glassy carbon surface and dried at 120°C for 2–3 min after each $2.5 \mu\text{L}$ addition to give a uniform coating. For the glucose oxidation measurements in blood, a glassy carbon plate was used (0.5 cm^2) with $45 \mu\text{L}$ of the artificial enzyme ink added on each side of the plate. The functionalization of the artificial enzymes with phenyl phosphor-ylcholine (PPC) was performed by cyclic voltammetry between 0.2 and -0.75 V (vs $\text{Ag}|\text{AgCl}|\text{NaCl}$ 3 mol L^{-1}) at 50 mV s^{-1} in PPC 5 mmol L^{-1} dissolved in HBF_4 0.1 mol L^{-1} where an equimolar amount of NaNO_2 was added under argon purging, which was maintained for 15 min before the measurements. The electrodes were rinsed with MilliQ water after the functionalization.

Electrochemical Measurements: Electrochemical Setup: The measurements in phosphate buffer (pH 7.4, $0.0302 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 + 0.0098 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ NaH_2PO_4) in the absence and the presence of chloride (KCl 100 mmol L^{-1}), human serum albumin (35 mg mL^{-1}) and interferents (ascorbic acid 0.11 mmol L^{-1} and uric acid 0.18 mmol L^{-1}) were conducted in a 12 mm diameter wide glass vial containing 1 mL of electrolyte. The measurements in blood were conducted in a 25 mm diameter wide glass vial containing 5 mL of electrolyte. In both setups, an $\text{Ag}|\text{AgCl}$ wire reference and a Pt plate counter electrode were used. The electrolyte was stirred in between measurements using a 3 mm stirring bar placed at the bottom of the vials. Different aliquots of glucose were added using a glass syringe from a 1 mol L^{-1} stock solution prepared 24 h prior and kept in dark at 4°C .

Electrochemical Measurements: Electrochemical Pulsing Protocol: In phosphate buffer, a series of 90 two-step potential pulses, consisting of a reduction pulse (-1.85 V for 0.2 s) and an oxidation pulse (-0.25 V for 0.1 s) were firstly performed in the absence of glucose until the oxidation current was stabilized (typically 6–10 repetitions). A $2 \mu\text{L}$ aliquot ($= 2 \text{ mmol L}^{-1}$, up to $12 \mu\text{L} = 12 \text{ mmol L}^{-1}$) of a 1 mol L^{-1} glucose solution was added into the electrolyte which was stirred for $\approx 30 \text{ s}$ before starting the measurement. The current at the end of each oxidation pulse was collected and summed up to produce the current versus glucose concentration plots. In whole blood, each measurement consisted of

10 repetitions of the series of 90 pulses without opening the circuit and the time of oxidation pulse was increased to 0.3 s.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

This research was financially supported by the National Health and Medical Research Council Investigator Grant (GNT1196648 JJG), Australian Research Council Discovery Projects (DP210102698 JJG and DP190102659 RDT), and the Mark Wainwright Analytical Centre (MWAC) at UNSW. S.V.S and J.W. acknowledge the Australian Government Research Training Scholarship for financial support. W.S. acknowledges the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (CasCat [833408]).

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available in the supplementary material of this article.

Keywords

electrochemistry, glucose, nanoconfinement, nanozymes, sensors, whole blood

Received: February 12, 2024
Revised: March 5, 2024
Published online:

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